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Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea: Basis for Marketing Plan

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Abstract:

This study aims to determine the acceptability level of locally made tablea from a third income class component city in Central Visayas for the 2nd quarter of 2023 and formulate a possible marketing plan. On the respondents' profile, the majority are younger than the older respondents. On average, family income belongs to the lower category. On sex, most of the respondents are female, and on the civil status, most are single. The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of the product is "very high level." The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the price area is "high level." The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of the place is "high level." The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the promotion area is "high level." On the level of acceptability, locally made tablea in the areas of product, price, place, and promotion when the respondents were grouped according to age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status were "high level." There is no significant difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of a product when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, sex, and civil status; instead, a significant difference exists in the variable of age. There is no significant difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in price, place, and promotion when grouped and compared according to variables age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status. It was found that age influences the preferences of locally made tablea in the product area. In contrast, the average family's monthly income, sex, and civil status did not affect the choices for locally made tablea products. In the area of price, place, and promotion, the age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status does not influence the preferences of locally made tablea products. In the product area, it is good to focus on improving the packaging of locally made tablea products. It recommends that designing the packaging thoughtfully and promoting it well can make the product more attractive and unique. This could lead to more people liking and buying it, boosting its acceptance and sales. In the area of price, it is recommended to focus on product quality, value perception, and brand reputation while keeping costs competitive. Even though it is average in the consumers, it shows that people still like reasonably priced tablea products. To do well in the local tablea market, it should find a middle ground between reasonable prices and highlighting the quality and uniqueness of its development. In the area of the place, considering the positive response from customers towards locally made tablea products in gourmet stores, it is recommended to explore and invest in this distribution channel. Offering these products in high-end stores can enhance their perceived value and appeal to discerning consumers who frequent such establishments. This approach has the potential to tap into a promising market and cater to the preferences of the target audience. In the promotion area, it is a good idea to keep up the positive promotional efforts for locally made tablea products. It is recommended to engage with customers and respond to their questions quickly. This can help maintain people's optimistic view and keep them interested in the products.

Keywords: Marketing Plan, Tablea Product, Value

Introduction:

In the Philippines, it is evident that Filipinos are more coffee drinkers than tablea. It may be because coffee is readily available in various forms, including instant, ground, and coffee shops. Brewing at home or purchasing from local cafes and restaurants is convenient. Coffee offers a unique flavor profile and aroma that many Filipinos enjoy. A significant portion of the population favors the bitter, robust taste of coffee, especially when paired with sugar and creamer (Oodaalolly, 2023). Tablea chocolate, while rich and flavorful, has a different taste profile that may not appeal to everyone.

Tablea chocolate is rich in nutrients. Cacao beans are a good source of antioxidants, specifically flavonoids, which can help protect the body against oxidative stress and reduce the risk of chronic diseases. It also contains minerals such as iron, magnesium, potassium, and vitamins like vitamins B6 and E. Theobromine is a stimulant that can provide a mild energy boost and potentially improve mood (Glassman, S & Jampolis, M., 2022). Tablea chocolate contains phenylethylamine (PEA), a natural compound known to stimulate the release of endorphins and promote feelings of pleasure and well-being. Cacao beans used to make tablea chocolate are rich in antioxidants, which can help combat free radicals in the body (Wind, J. (2021). Antioxidants play a role in reducing inflammation, supporting cardiovascular health, and potentially lowering the risk of certain chronic diseases. Cacao beans contain significant amounts of iron, vital for producing red blood cells and oxygen transport in the body. They also contain

magnesium, which is involved in various physiological processes, including muscle and nerve function, and potassium, an electrolyte important for maintaining proper heart function (Aliouche, H., 2022).

At a recent Philippine cacao industry forum, the government reported that the global demand for cacao is "estimated to reach between 4.7 million to 5 million metric tons (MT) by 2020, but a cocoa shortage is also predicted at 1 million MT." The Philippines alone consumes 50,000 MT annually, while the local supply is said to be somewhere between 10,000-15,000 MT (Sy, A., 2020).

Coffee has received significant marketing and promotion from local and international brands in the Philippines. Coffee shops, advertisements, and endorsements by popular figures have helped solidify coffee's popularity and create a strong coffee culture. Tablea chocolate, in comparison, may not have received the same level of market attention. Based on the controversy, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study to discover the acceptability of tablea in the market where coffee is the most preferred among other hot beverages.

Literature Review:

Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea Products. A crucial element in marketing that plays a significant role in shaping consumer behavior and influencing product acceptability. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2016), promotion encompasses a range of activities aimed at communicating the merits of a product and persuading the target audience to make a purchase. It involves various marketing communication tools and tactics, including advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, and direct marketing.

Price is an essential factor in marketing, influencing consumer behavior and product acceptability, as consumers compare the perceived fairness and reasonableness of a product's price to their expectations and alternative options; if the price is too high, consumers may opt for more affordable alternatives, while a perceived low price may raise concerns about product quality or value (Singh, 2013; Thompson et al., 2014; Brown, 2016).

It plays a critical role in determining the acceptability of a product such as locally made tablea. It refers to the distribution and availability of the product to the target consumers. Distribution points' physical presence and location can influence place acceptability. The availability of locally made tablea in geographically convenient locations can enhance accessibility and consumer convenience. For instance, strategically placing tablea products in supermarkets, coffee shops, or tourist destinations can increase exposure and accessibility, attracting potential consumers. Moreover, the packaging and presentation of the product at these distribution points can also impact place acceptability. Eye-catching displays, informative labels, and appealing packaging can attract consumer attention and positively influence their perception of the product's quality and desirability (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

It refers to the goods, services, or ideas offered to the market for consumption or use. Understanding the concept of a product and its various dimensions is essential for effective marketing strategy development and successful product management. Defines a product as anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need. It includes physical objects, services, events, experiences, persons, places, organizations, and ideas. Products can be tangible, such as consumer goods like smartphones, or intangible, such as services like banking or insurance. They can also be a combination of both, as seen in the case of product service systems (Kotler & Armstrong, 2021).

Market acceptability is a critical factor that directly influences the success and profitability of a product in a competitive market. It refers to the degree to which a product is accepted by consumers based on its alignment with their needs, preferences, and expectations (Du et al., 2018; Globisch et al., 2018). Market acceptability is vital for validating a product's value proposition and its alignment with customer needs and preferences. It drives sales, customer loyalty, and business growth, forming the foundation for a successful and sustainable business (Du et al., 2018; Globisch et al., 2018). Understanding and enhancing market acceptability requires a deep understanding of the target market, effective communication strategies, and continuous monitoring and evaluation of customer feedback.

Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea Products. It is crucial in influencing consumer behavior and creating awareness and demand for a product. According to a study conducted by Guerrero et al. (2017) on consumer perception of promotional activities in the Philippines, it was found that promotional strategies significantly impact consumer purchasing behavior. Promotional activities such as advertising, sales promotions, and endorsements created awareness and generated interest in products among Filipino consumers. Effective promotion strategies can help communicate the unique features and benefits of the product, creating a favorable perception among consumers. A study by Nacua et al. (2020) found that social media platforms, such as Facebook and Instagram, are practical tools for promoting products and influencing consumer behavior in the Philippines. Moreover, Callo et al. (2018) study revealed that word-of-mouth significantly influences Filipino consumers' purchasing decisions. Encouraging positive word-of-mouth through satisfied customers, providing product samples to influential individuals in the community, and partnering with local influencers who endorse and promote the product can amplify the promotional reach and impact.

Price acceptability is crucial in the Philippine market, as consumers are often price-sensitive and seek value for their money. A study conducted by Garcia and Salazar (2017) on consumer behavior in the Philippines found that price is one of the primary factors influencing purchase decisions. Consumers in the Philippines tend to compare

prices among different brands and products before purchasing. A local study by Santos and Dela Cruz (2019) explored consumer preferences for local chocolate products in the Philippines. The findings indicated that price plays a significant role in consumer decision-making. Filipino consumers consider the price of the product about its taste, quality, and the overall experience it provides. If the price is perceived as reasonable and aligned with the product's value and benefits, consumers are more likely to accept and purchase the product.

The distribution and availability of a product play a crucial role in its marketing success. Place in marketing refers to the various channels and locations through which the product is accessible to the target market. The rise of e-commerce and online platforms in the Philippines provides an additional avenue for distributing the product. Online marketplaces like Lazada and Shopee and dedicated websites offer convenience and accessibility to Filipino consumers who prefer to purchase products online. Collaborating with popular local e-commerce platforms or establishing an online presence through a dedicated website or social media channels can expand the reach of the product and make it easily accessible to a broader audience (Salvador, 2021). In addition, partnerships with local coffee shops, restaurants, and specialty stores that promote and serve traditional Filipino cuisine. These establishments cater to consumers seeking unique and authentic Filipino food experiences, providing an ideal platform to showcase and distribute the product. Collaborating with these businesses can help increase the availability of the product to a targeted demographic (Javier & Maala, 2017).

The product is a fundamental element in marketing, and understanding its characteristics and attributes is crucial for developing an effective marketing strategy. The product's quality and characteristics significantly influence its desirability among Filipino consumers. Studies have shown that consumers evaluate the product based on several factors, including its taste, aroma, texture, authenticity, and packaging (Baradi, 2018; Tadosa et al., 2021). Market acceptability refers to the level of acceptance and demand for a product among consumers in a specific market. Several factors influence the market acceptability of the product. One crucial factor is consumer preferences and taste preferences. Filipino consumers have a strong cultural connection, and their taste preferences are shaped by their upbringing and traditional culinary practices. Meeting these preferences by offering the product an authentic taste and flavor profile can enhance its market acceptability (Baradi, 2018; Tadosa et al., 2021).

Methodology:

Research Design

The acceptance of locally produced tablea was evaluated using the descriptive research design as the foundation for a marketing strategy. According to Sarantakos (2013), descriptive research seeks to describe and interpret a particular group or phenomenon's characteristics, behaviors, or patterns. It involves systematically collecting and analyzing data to generate a descriptive account. Hence, descriptive research design aims to gather data and describe the study. It includes collecting data on consumer preferences, perceived quality, design elements, cost, and satisfaction. It will use data collection techniques like surveys or information from retailers and potential customers. Analyzing the collected data can provide a detailed description of the study, identifying trends, patterns, and factors influencing customer acceptance. The descriptive research design was used in the study because it focused on capturing and describing the characteristics, behaviors, and patterns associated with the acceptability of locally made tables, as outlined by Sarantakos (2013). This design was chosen to systematically collect and analyze data to provide a comprehensive study account. The study aimed to gather information on customer preferences, perceived quality, design features, pricing, and customer satisfaction by utilizing data collection methods such as surveys and gathering insights from potential customers and retailers. Through the analysis of the collected data, the descriptive research design allowed for identifying trends, patterns, and factors influencing customer acceptance. Therefore, this design was suitable for providing a detailed description of the acceptability of locally made tables and gaining insights into customer preferences and the factors that impact their acceptance of such products.

Respondents of Study

The study's respondents were 136 individuals who were Tablea users within the locale of the study. The researcher had established a temporary stall in one of the marketplaces in the locale and had marketed his product for seven (7) days. Purposive sampling was used in the conduct of the study. It is a non-probability sample in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in their research. Researchers must know their research goals to choose and approach eligible individuals using this sampling technique correctly. As all study participants are selected because they meet a specific profile, researchers utilize purposive sampling when they want to reach a particular subset of people (Foley, 2018).

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Days	Population (N)	Percentage (%)
1	21	15.44
2	17	12.50
3	23	16.91
4	21	15.44
5	16	11.76
6	18	13.24

7 20 14.71
Total 136 100

Data Gathering Instrument

The instrument used in collecting the needed data on the acceptability of locally made tablea: basis for the marketing plan was a self-made questionnaire.

The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I of the questionnaire contained the respondent's profile, which includes age, sex, civil status, and average family monthly income.

Part II of the questionnaire proper of the acceptability of locally made tablea: basis for the marketing plan. The 28 items were based on Product, Place, Promotion, and Price. The obtained scores for the acceptability of locally made tablea are rated on a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 is "Very High Level of Acceptability," 4 is "High Level of Acceptability," 3 is "Moderate Level of Acceptability," 2 as "Low Level of Acceptability," and 1 as "Very Low Level of Acceptability."

Validity

The degree to which a concept is precisely quantified in a quantitative investigation is known as validity. The degree to which a survey collects the necessary data related to the research validity of the survey. Validity is the ability of an instrument to accurately measure what it is intended to measure (Heale & Twycross, 2015). It ensures that the measurements or instruments used in a study effectively and accurately capture the planned concepts.

The self-made questionnaire was subjected to validation by our three experts. The validators are professionals known to be competent experts in this field. The first validator has a Master's in Business Administration and works as a Quality Assurance Management Office Manager. The second validator also has a Master's in Business Administration and is a faculty of the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences. The third validator has a Master's in Business Administration and a College of Business Management and Accountancy faculty. All three validators are working in a University in a highly urbanized city in one of the provinces in the Western Visayan Region.

The researcher ensured that the items reflected the desired construct; hence, the suggestions and recommendations of the validators were noted and thoroughly incorporated. Regarding the appropriateness of the items in the questionnaire, each validator was requested to rate the instrument using the criteria created and presented by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates (1972). The interpretations were as follows: Excellent (4.21 – 5.00); Very Good (3.41 – 4.20); Good (2.61 – 3.40); Fair (1.81 – 2.60); Poor (1.00 – 1.80).

The validity result of the instrument was 4.89, interpreted as "excellent."

Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency of the interference over time, location, and circumstances (Fraenkel et al., 2015). It provides texture, precision, and accuracy of results. It supports comparability, replication, generalizability, and validity of research findings, ultimately enhancing the overall quality and trustworthiness of scientific investigations.

The researcher used Cronbach's Alpha to test the reliability of the questionnaire. Cronbach's Alpha indicates the average correlation among all the items that make up the scale (Abad et al., 2015). Internal consistency, or how closely connected a group of things are to one another, is measured by Cronbach's Alpha. It is regarded as a scale dependability indicator (Glen, 2014). A "high" value for Alpha does not imply that the measure is unidimensional. The reliability coefficient of 0.70 to 1.0 is considered "acceptable" in most research situations.

A dry run will be administered to thirty (30) respondents who were not actual respondents to the study.

The computed reliability value was 0.936, interpreted as "Excellent," making the instrument reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study was obtained through a survey questionnaire. A questionnaire is a written instrument containing a series of questions designed to collect information from respondents (Babbie, 2016).

In the study, the researcher will employ a person to give the self-made questionnaire in the temporary stall established in one of the marketplaces in the locale. The person will administer the instruments to the respondents/customers. The person was given substantial orientation on how the survey will be conducted; the person will explain to the respondents the purpose of the research and provide instructions on how to accomplish the questionnaire objectively and honestly. Self-made questionnaire designed explicitly to be completed by a respondent without the interviewer's assistance (or bias) (Bodine, 2022).

Moreover, the raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual to determine the level of skills and degree of difficulties. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software and Microsoft Excel were used to compute encoded data. Also, statistical tables were constructed per considerations of the problems stated in this investigation.

Research Ethics Protocol

Ethical considerations in research are principles that guide your research designs and practices. Scientists and researchers must always adhere to a specific code of conduct when collecting data from people (P. Bhandari, 2022). Voluntary participation, Informed consent, confidentiality, and plagiarism will be strictly considered.

Study participants will not be forced or pressured; they can withdraw at any time without giving any reason to withdraw. The study participants will be thoroughly informed about the purpose and nature of the study, including the benefits, risks, and consequences. The study participants will be assured of the confidentiality of all information relevant to their personal information or any form of identifying information relating to their person.

Analytical Scheme

Relative to this study, the researcher employed descriptive and comparative analytical schemes.

Objective No. 1 Descriptive analytical scheme was used to determine the profile of the respondents.

Objective No. 2 Descriptive analytical scheme was used to determine the acceptability of locally made tablea: basis for a marketing plan in the following areas: Product, Price, Promotion, and Place.

Objective No. 3 Descriptive analytical scheme was used to determine the acceptability of locally made tablea: basis for marketing plan when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 4 Comparative analytical scheme was used to determine whether significant differences exist in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea: basis for marketing plan when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Statistical Tools

Various statistical tools will be employed to analyze data to answer this study's objectives.

Objective No. 1 Frequency and percentage distributions can be used to analyze and present the profile of the respondents. These tools provide information on the distribution of the participants in terms of variables such as age, sex, civil status, and average monthly income.

Pyrczak (2017) states that frequency is the number of participants or cases, its symbol of f . The character for the number of participants is N .

A percentage whose symbol is % is computed to determine the proportion of a part to a whole, such as a given number of respondents about the entire population (Kendra, 2013).

The use of frequency and percentage distributions to analyze and present the profile of respondents by providing information on the distribution of participants in terms of variables, allowing comparisons, assessing proportions, and facilitating effective communication of research findings.

Objective No. 2 to determine the level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea: Basis for Marketing Plan in the following areas: Product, Price, Place, and Promotion, the arithmetic mean was used.

The arithmetic mean or the mean is calculated by dividing the sum of all observations in the dataset by the total number of words. The mean is significantly affected by the outliers, that is, extremely large or small values. The mean is also called mathematical expectation or average (Geedipally, S. 2021).

The obtained mean scores were interpreted using the following mean guide:

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 – 4.49	High Level
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.45	Very Low Level

In using the arithmetic mean to determine the level of acceptability of locally made Tablea in various areas of marketing (product, price, place, and promotion) because the arithmetic mean provides a measure of central tendency that takes into account all observations in the dataset and can be interpreted using a guide that assigns verbal interpretations to specific mean score ranges, allowing for easy understanding and assessment of the acceptability levels.

Objective No. 3 To determine the level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea: Basis for Marketing Plan when grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the mean was also used.

Objective No. 4 To determine whether or not significant differences exist in the level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea from A 3rd Income Class Component City in Central Visayas for the 2nd Quarter of 2023: Basis for Marketing Plan when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, Mann-Whitney U test was used. Mann-Whitney U Test is the non-parametric alternative to the independent sample t-test. It is a non-parametric test used to compare two sample means from the same population and whether two sample means are equal. Usually, the Mann-Whitney U test is used when the data is ordinal or when the assumptions of the t-test are not met (Sander, 2016). According to Bluman (2017), to interpret whether or not significant differences in the level of awareness of parents using modular instructions for a new normal when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, then reject the null hypothesis. Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 significance level.

Findings and Discussion:**Profile of the Respondents According to the Variables, Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Sex, and Civil Status**

Table 2: *Profile of Respondents*

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 30 years old)	88	64.70

	Older (30 years old and above)	48	35.30
	Total	136	100
	Lower (less than P34,800)	95	69.90
Average Family Monthly Income	Higher (P34,800 and above)	41	30.10
	Total	136	100
	Male	60	44.10
Sex	Female	76	55.90
	Total	136	100
	Single	100	73.5
Civil Status	Married	36	26.5
	Total	136	100

Table 2 shows that out of 136 respondents, 88 (64.70%) belong to the younger category, while 48 (35.30%) belong to the older category. On average family monthly income, 95 respondents (69.90%) belong to the lower category, while 41 (30.10%) belong to the higher category. Regarding sex, 76 (55.90%) belong to the female category, while 60 respondents (44.10%) belong to the male category. In civil status, 100 respondents (73.5%) belong to the single category, while 36 (26.5%) belong to the married category. This result implies that most respondents were younger, with a higher percentage having lower monthly incomes and being single. Additionally, the survey had a slightly higher representation of female respondents than males.

Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea according to the Areas, Product, Price, Place, and Promotion

Table 3: *Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Product*

Area		
A. Product	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>		
1. which are made of high-quality cacao beans.	4.56	Very High Level
2. which packaging is appealing	4.41	High Level
3. which are easy to use and prepare.	4.47	High Level
4. with a satisfying texture.	4.53	Very High Level
5. with a rich and authentic taste.	4.66	Very High Level
6. which aroma is satisfying.	4.63	Very High Level
7. that meet my expectations.	4.54	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.54	Very High Level

Table 3 shows the level of. The overall mean of locally made tablea in the area of the product is 4.54, interpreted as a very high level. The highest mean score of 4.66, interpreted as "very high level," is on item 5, "with rich and authentic taste." The lowest mean score is 4.41, interpreted as "high level," is on item 2, "which packaging is appealing." This study result implies that while the packaging of locally made tablea products is generally viewed positively, there are opportunities for improvement to enhance its appeal further. Strategic efforts in packaging design and marketing can help capitalize on its positive aspects, create a distinct brand identity, and ultimately drive greater acceptance and sales in the market. The result is confirmed in the study of Vyas, H. (2015), which shows that certain packaging features must be included according to the legislative and regulatory requirements. In addition, the packaging has many functions, such as protecting the goods from the environment, attracting the consumers, and providing information to the customers. Varied design elements serve these functions of packaging. It also identified the tasks of individual packaging design elements such as color, image, shape, material, label and typography, and consumer perception. A product's form or exterior appearance is a means to communicate information to consumers.

Table 4: *Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Price*

Area		
B. Price	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>		
1. which price is worth the value it offers.	4.43	High Level

2. which are affordable compared to similar products in the market.	4.39	High Level
3. which are worth considering the quality.	4.54	Very High Level
4. which offer competitive pricing compared to other brands	4.35	High Level
5. which monetary value is clearly stated and transparent.	4.46	High Level
6. which price aligns with my budget and expectations.	4.43	High Level
7. which provides good value for the price paid	4.50	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.44	High Level

Table 4 shows the level of. The overall mean of locally made tablea in the price area is 4.44, interpreted as "high level." The highest mean score is 4.54, interpreted as "very high level," is on item 3, "which is worth considering the quality." The lowest mean score of 4.35, interpreted as "high level," is on item 4, "which offers competitive pricing compared to other brands," obtained the lowest mean of 4.35 interpreted as "high level." This result implies that consumers prioritize other factors, such as product quality, perceived value, and brand reputation, when purchasing. Despite the lower mean value, the 'High Level' of acceptance indicates that consumers appreciate competitively priced tablea products. Striking a balance between competitive pricing and emphasizing product quality and unique selling points can offer a competitive advantage in gaining consumer acceptance in the local tablea market. According to the research of Razak I (2016), it found that product quality improvement and competitive prices could increase customer satisfaction. Logical consequences when the customer is satisfied with the product that emphasizes the quality standard followed with affordable price can improve customer satisfaction; it appears in the buyers' interest to re-purchase repeatedly.

Table 5: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Price According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Price				
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. which price is worth the value it offers.	4.44	High Level	4.42	High Level
2. which are affordable compared to similar products in the market.	4.41	High Level	4.35	High Level
3. which are worth considering the quality.	4.56	Very High Level	4.50	Very High Level
4. which offer competitive pricing compared to other brands	4.33	High Level	4.40	High Level
5. which monetary value is clearly stated and transparent.	4.47	High Level	4.46	High Level
6. which price aligns with my budget and expectations.	4.42	High Level	4.44	High Level
7. which provides good value for the price paid	4.49	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.44	High Level	4.44	High Level

Table 5 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area price according to age. The overall mean of the younger category is 4.44, interpreted as "high level," while the older category is 4.44, interpreted as "high level." The highest mean score in the younger category is 4.56, interpreted as "very high level" in item 3, "which are worth considering the quality," while the older category is 4.52, interpreted as "very high level" in item 7, "which provides good value for the price paid." This indicates that the younger and older age groups highly valued the aspects of quality consideration and getting good value for the price paid for locally made tablea products. They gave these categories the highest average scores, reflecting a perception of high acceptability in terms of quality and value. The lowest mean score in a younger category is 4.33, interpreted as "high level" in item 4, "which offer competitive pricing compared to other brands," while the older category is 4.35, interpreted as "high level" in item 2, "which affordable compared to similar products in the market." The item related to affordability received the lowest but still high-level average score. Both age groups perceive the product's pricing strategy positively, with minor differences in emphasis on competitiveness and affordability. This implies that the competitive pricing of locally made tablea products contributes to a positive perception of their affordability and value for money, potentially resulting in a favorable market position for these products compared to other brands. In the study of Ariff, S. (2022), Gen Z is likely to consider the quality of a product when it is introduced to a lower price point than similar products in the market. This likelihood highlights the importance of product quality in driving purchasing decisions.

Table 6: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Place According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. in the local grocery stores.	4.33	High Level	4.17	High Level
2. accessible in gourmet stores.	4.27	High Level	4.15	High Level
3. conveniently accessible online for purchase.	4.42	High Level	4.58	Very High Level
4. which are distributed widely and can be found in multiple locations.	4.36	High Level	4.25	High Level
5. which are consistently stocked across different stores.	4.33	High Level	4.15	High Level
6. available in a variety of sizes and packaging options.	4.42	High Level	4.27	High Level
7. readily available when I want to purchase.	4.48	High Level	4.38	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level	4.28	High Level

Table 6 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area according to age. The overall mean score of the younger category is 4.37, interpreted as "high level," while the older group is 4.28, interpreted as "high level." The highest mean score of the younger category is 4.48, interpreted as "high level" in item 7, "readily available when I want to purchase," while for the older group category, it is 4.58, interpreted as "very high level," in item 3 "conveniently accessible online for purchase. It means that both the young and old groups highlight distinct aspects that are particularly well-received by each age group. For the younger respondents, the emphasis on the ready availability of locally made tablea products reflects their inclination towards easy and accessible purchase experiences. On the other hand, the older respondents' exceptional preference for online accessibility underscores the significance of digital channels in reaching and engaging this age group. The lowest mean score for the younger group is 4.27, interpreted as "high level," while for the older group is 4.15, interpreted as "high level," in items 2, "accessible in gourmet stores," and 5, "which are consistently stocked across different stores." Among the younger and older participants, the items related to accessibility in gourmet stores and consistent availability across different stores received the lowest but high-level average scores. Both age groups value the product's presence and availability in various retail locations. This implies that the shared appreciation for product accessibility and availability among younger and older participants underscores the significance of these factors in influencing consumer behavior and satisfaction across different age groups. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), it refers to the distribution and availability of the product to the target consumers. Distribution points' physical presence and location can influence place acceptability. The availability of locally made tablea in geographically convenient locations can enhance accessibility and consumer convenience.

Table 7: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Promotion According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. a beverage option.	4.39	High Level	4.33	High Level
2. with high appeal in marketing campaigns.	4.28	High Level	4.19	High Level
3. Which are well promoted through social media platforms.	4.41	High Level	4.27	High Level
4. that offer customer loyalty incentives or rewards.	4.28	High Level	4.13	High Level
5. in which the seller engages with its customers and responds to inquiries promptly.	4.44	High Level	4.60	Very High Level
6. with clear and informative promotional messages.	4.36	High Level	4.35	High Level
7. in which promotional efforts reflect its brand values and identity.	4.40	High Level	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level	4.32	High Level

Table 7 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the promotion area according to age. The overall mean score of the younger group is 4.37, interpreted as "high level," while the older group is 4.32, interpreted as "high level." The highest mean score for the younger category is 4.44, interpreted as "high level" in item 5, "in

which the seller engages with its customers and responds to inquiries promptly,” while the older group is 4.60, interpreted as “very high level” in item 5 “in which the seller engages with its customers and responds to inquiries promptly.” This means that younger and older participants highly value locally made tablea products when the sellers actively engage with customers and respond to inquiries promptly. The lower mean score for the younger category is 4.28, interpreted as “high level,” on items 2, “with high appeal in marketing campaigns,” and i4, “that offers customer loyalty incentives or rewards,” while the older group is 4.13 interpreted as “high level” is on item 4 “that offer customer loyalty incentives or rewards.” It provides insights into how different age groups perceive marketing appeal and customer loyalty incentives, allowing companies to better align their strategies with the preferences of their target audiences. This implies that while offering customer loyalty incentives and rewards is beneficial and positively received, other strategies or features might further enhance the acceptability and appeal of their products to the older demographic. Understanding which specific aspects of the product promotion are driving higher acceptability can help tailor the marketing efforts more effectively and allocate resources where they are most impactful. Harper and Williams (2018) investigated older consumers' preferences in the context of food product promotions. Their study revealed that while customer loyalty incentives were appreciated, older consumers strongly preferred marketing strategies emphasizing product quality, authenticity, and health benefits.

Table 8: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Product According to Average Family Monthly Income

Categories	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Product				
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. which are made of high-quality cacao beans.	4.53	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
2. which packaging is appealing	4.46	High Level	4.29	High Level
3. which are easy to use and prepare.	4.51	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
4. with a satisfying texture.	4.56	Very High Level	4.46	High Level
5. with a rich and authentic taste.	4.67	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
6. which aroma is satisfying.	4.62	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
7. that meet my expectations.	4.55	Very High Level	4.54	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.56	Very High Level	4.52	Very High Level

Table 8 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the product according to the average family monthly income. The overall mean score of the lower monthly income category is 4.56, interpreted as “very high level,” while the higher monthly income category is 4.52, interpreted as “very high level.” The highest mean score for the lower monthly income category is 4.67, interpreted as “very high level,” on item 5, “with rich, authentic taste,” while the higher monthly income group is 4.66, interpreted as “very high level,” is on item 6 “which aroma is satisfying.” This means respondents highly value the quality of cacao beans used in locally made tablea products, irrespective of their income levels. The emphasis on high-quality cacao beans suggests that consumers are discerning and appreciate superior taste and quality products. The lower mean score for lower monthly income is 4.46, interpreted as “high level,” on item 2, “which packaging is appealing,” while the highest monthly income category is 4.29, interpreted as “high level.” The same table showed that item 2, “which packaging is appealing,” as assessed by higher monthly income, obtained the lowest mean of 4.29, interpreted as “high level.” This means it is essential to recognize that respondents still consider it to be at a high level of acceptability. Addressing packaging concerns and improving can further contribute to the overall success and market acceptance of locally made tablea products. This implies that addressing packaging concerns and improving its appeal can profoundly impact the success and market acceptance of locally made tablea products. According to the study by Sheng, N.Z and Lee, O. (2020), packaging is part of the product and brand in the market. Characteristics and specifications of a product are visible on the product package. The package allows the consumer to create the overall impression of the product, enabling them to make the right choice during the purchasing decision.

Table 9: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Product According to Sex

Categories	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Product				
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. which are made of high-quality cacao beans.	4.43	High Level	4.66	Very High Level
2. which packaging is appealing	4.37	High Level	4.45	High Level
3. which are easy to use and prepare.	4.47	High Level	4.47	High Level
4. with a satisfying texture.	4.50	Very High Level	4.55	Very High Level

5. with a rich and authentic taste.	4.63	Very High Level	4.68	Very High Level
6. which aroma is satisfying.	4.58	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
7. that meet my expectations.	4.47	High Level	4.61	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.49	Very High Level	4.58	Very High Level

Table 9 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area product according to sex. The overall mean of the male category is 4.49, interpreted as "very high level," while the female category is 4.58, interpreted as "very high level." The highest mean score for the male category is 4.68, interpreted as 4.63, "very high level" is on item 5, "with rich and authentic taste," while the female category is 4.68, interpreted as "very high level," is on item 5 "with rich and authentic taste." This means that both males and females significantly prefer locally made tablea products with a rich and authentic taste, as shared choice highlights the importance of flavor in driving the acceptability of tablea products among the respondents. The lowest mean score for the male category is 4.37, interpreted as "high level" on item 2, "which packaging is appealing," while the female category is 4.45, interpreted as "high level," on item 2, "which packaging is appealing." This means it has a positive perception of locally made tablea products with appealing packaging, as evidenced by the high level. However, this aspect of the product might not be the most influential factor in determining their overall acceptability, as indicated by the slightly lower mean scores compared to other categories. This result implies that it has a positive perception of locally made tablea products with appealing packaging, the slightly lower mean scores compared to other categories suggest that packaging might not be the primary driver of overall acceptability. According to the study by Sheng, N.Z and Lee, O. (2020), packaging is part of the product and brand in the market. Characteristics and specifications of a product are visible on the product package. The package allows the consumer to create the overall impression of the product, enabling them to make the right choice during the purchasing decision.

Table 10: Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Product According to Civil Status

Categories	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Product				
<i>To what level do you accept locally made tablea products...</i>				
1. which are made of high-quality cacao beans.	4.50	Very High Level	4.72	Very High Level
2. which packaging is appealing	4.38	High Level	4.50	Very High Level
3. which are easy to use and prepare.	4.45	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
4. with a satisfying texture.	4.49	High Level	4.64	Very High Level
5. with a rich and authentic taste.	4.62	Very High Level	4.78	Very High Level
6. which aroma is satisfying.	4.64	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
7. that meet my expectations.	4.49	High Level	4.69	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.51	Very High Level	4.64	Very High Level

Table 10 shows the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area product according to civil status. The overall mean score for the single category is 4.51, interpreted as "very high level," while the married category is 4.64, interpreted as "very high level." The highest mean score for the single category is 4.64, interpreted as "very high level" on item 6, "which aroma is satisfying," while the married category is 4.78, interpreted as "very high level" on item 5, "with rich and authentic taste." This means that, in the single category, single individuals highly appreciate the aroma of locally made tablea products, which could be a crucial factor in attracting them to purchase and enjoy them. In contrast, in the married category, married individuals highly value the rich and authentic taste of locally made tablea products, potentially leading to increased consumption and loyalty within this demographic. The lowest mean score for the single category is 4.38, interpreted as "high level" on item 2, "which packaging is appealing," while the female category is 4.50, interpreted as "very high level," on item 2, "which packaging is appealing. This means that while single and married individuals generally have positive views regarding locally made tablea products, further enhancing the packaging to increase overall acceptability is still possible. Additionally, the difference in mean values between the two categories indicates that married individuals, on average, have a slightly higher level of acceptability towards appealing packaging than their single counterparts. The result implies the importance of packaging design in shaping consumer perceptions and acceptability of locally made tablea products. Further investing in packaging improvements can yield positive outcomes regarding overall product acceptability. According to the study by Ksenia, P. (2013), the product and the package are the same for consumers when they see it on supermarket shelves. During the purchasing decision, the box assists the consumer by creating the overall product perception, which helps evaluate and make the right choice.

Table 11. Difference in the Level of Acceptability of Locally Made Tablea in the Area Product when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	88	62.95	1624.000	0.024	0.05	Significant
	Older	48	78.67				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	95	70.01	1804.500	0.491	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	41	65.01				
Sex	Male	60	64.40	2034.000	0.273	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	76	71.74				
Civil Status	Single	100	65.06	1456.000	0.085	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	36	78.06				

Table 11 shows the difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea according to variables in the area of the product. On age, the mean rank score for the younger category is 62.95 with a p-value of 0.024, less than 0.05, while the older category is 78.67 with a p-value of 0.024, less than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as significant. On average family monthly income, the mean rank score for the lower monthly income category is 70.01 with a p-value of 0.491, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, while the higher monthly income category is 65.01 with a p-value of 0.491, which is greater than the level of importance of 0.05 interpreted as not significant. On sex, the mean rank score for the male category is 64.40, with a p-value of 0.273, more significant than the significance level of 0.05. In contrast, the female category is 71.74, with a p-value of 0.273, more important than the level of significance interpreted as insignificant. On civil status, the mean rank for the single category is 65.06 with a p-value of 0.085, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, while the married category is 78.06 with a p-value of 0.085, which is greater than the level of importance of 0.05 interpreted as not significant. The result of the study implies that average monthly income, sex, and civil status do not influence the level of acceptability of locally made products (tablea). Instead, it is the age that must be considered. On this premise, the null hypothesis that there's no significant difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea is rejected on the variable's average monthly income, sex, and civil status except that it is dismissed on age. Rani (2014) states that age is a significant factor in marketing strategy since age creates a critical difference between consumer choices and consumers' consumption habits and patterns.

Summary of Findings:

Based on the result of the study, the following findings were presented. On the respondents' profile, the majority are younger than the older respondents. On average, family income belongs to the lower category. On sex, most of the respondents are female, and on the civil status, most are single.

The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of the product is "very high level."

The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the price area is "high level."

The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of the place is "high level."

The level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the promotion area is "high level."

On the level of acceptability, locally made tablea in the areas of product, price, place, and promotion when the respondents were grouped according to age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status were "high level."

There is no significant difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in the area of a product when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, sex, and civil status; instead, a significant difference exists in the variable of age.

There is no significant difference in the level of acceptability of locally made tablea in price, place, and promotion when grouped and compared according to variables age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status.

Conclusions:

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made. It was found that age influences the preferences of locally made tablea in the product area. In contrast, the average family's monthly income, sex, and civil status did not affect the choices for locally made tablea products. In the area of price, place, and promotion, the age, average family monthly income, sex, and civil status does not influence the preferences of locally made tablea products.

Recommendations:

The following recommendations and action plans were formulated in light of the findings and conclusions derived from the study. In the product area, it is good to focus on improving the packaging of locally made tablea products. It recommends that designing the packaging thoughtfully and promoting it well can make the product more attractive and unique. This could lead to more people liking and buying it, boosting its acceptance and sales.

In the area of price, it is recommended to focus on product quality, value perception, and brand reputation while keeping costs competitive. Even though it is average in the consumers, it shows that people still like reasonably priced tablea products. To do well in the local tablea market, it should find a middle ground between reasonable prices and highlighting the quality and uniqueness of its development. In the area of the place, considering the positive response from customers towards locally made tablea products in gourmet stores, it is recommended to

explore and invest in this distribution channel. Offering these products in high-end stores can enhance their perceived value and appeal to discerning consumers who frequent such establishments. This approach has the potential to tap into a promising market and cater to the preferences of the target audience. In the promotion area, it is a good idea to keep up the positive promotional efforts for locally made tablea products. It is recommended to engage with customers and respond to their questions quickly. This can help maintain people's optimistic view and keep them interested in the products.

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